

Research Article

Status of Technological Capacity Building in the Indigenous Oilfield Servicing Firms in Nigeria vis-a-vis Innovation Capability

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Abstract

This paper assessed the factors that promote technological capacity building in the indigenous oilfield servicing firms in Nigeria. This was with a view to providing information that will increase indigenous participation in the sector and value addition for the nation. The study used primary and secondary data sources. Structured questionnaire were administered in the firms. This was supplemented with shop-floor observations and interviews. The questionnaires elicited information on the factors influencing firms' capability for innovation in the sector. A total of 60 questionnaires were administered to the heads of technical, finance and administration departments in the firms with 67% response rate. Secondary data were sourced from the internet and other publications. The data obtained were analysed using descriptive statistics. The important factors that accounted for the firms' technological capability (TC) included the qualifications and experience of the heads of technical departments and extensive staff training. In conclusion, the most significant driver of TC building in the firms was the educational level of the head(s) of technical department(s).

Keywords: Local content, Oil and Gas industry, Technological Capability, Innovation

Introduction

The Oil and Gas Industry (OGI) in Nigeria plays a crucial role to sustaining the nation by fuelling her economic and development activities. The industry has been widely described as the nation's live wire and literature abounds on its role and significance in Nigeria (Agusto, 2002; Atakpu, 2007; Odulari, 2008). Nonetheless, an estimated \$8 billion is spent annually on servicing the industry in operations such as fabrication, engineering, procurement and construction (EPC), front end engineering design (FEED), conceptual designs and seismic studies. This figure is projected to hit \$15 billion within the next few years (BPSES, 2008; Odulari, 2008). Regrettably, despite these huge sums of money spent in servicing the industry, only a very little proportion of the accruable profit is spent in Nigeria. Majority of the amounts are repatriated abroad, where most of the equipments are manufactured; and providing employment opportunities for citizens of other countries. The major reason for this situation has been attributed to low local content (LC), which is a situation where most of the service contracts are awarded to foreign firms because indigenous firms lack the requisite skills, technical expertise, manpower and production capacity and capability to compete favourably. Oladele (2001) attributed the low LC in the Nigerian OGI to insufficient capital, poor training, and low corporate image. Aneke (2002) and Heum *et al.* (2003) expanded the above reasons for low local content in Nigeria to include: low technological capacity; lack of funding from financial institutions; inadequate and incoherent policies/legislations; inadequate infrastructure; unfavourable business climate; lack of partnering between indigenous contractors and technically competent foreign companies. This paper zeros in on technological capability as an indispensable asset for the OGI in Nigeria. Technological capability is defined as the resources needed to generate and manage production-based and innovative activities such as improvements in processes and production organisation, products, equipment, and engineering projects (Aderemi, 2010; Figueiredo, 2007). These are accumulated and embodied in individuals (skills, expertise and experience) and organisational routines and systems. The authors in this paper seek to examine the factors that contribute to the development of TC as a resource in the Nigeria OGI.

Since the last five decades, the Nigerian Oil and Gas Industry have continued to play a key role in the country's economic growth and development. The sector generates about 95 percent of total export revenue and 80 percent of her total national income. In addition, it expends about \$8 billion annually in servicing its operations. Sadly, a

significant proportion of this amount is paid to foreign contractors for services like fabrication and engineering procurement; resulting into capital flight and leaving very little to developing the country's industrial base. Similarly, the 'Local Content' (LC) policy, aimed at championing the course for higher indigenous participation in the sector and value addition for the nation have not been implemented cause the indigenous firms lack the required technological capability.

Literature Review

It is generally agreed in the literature on growth and competitiveness that a country needs technological capabilities before it can grow sustainably; and that it acquires this primarily through learning (Garvin, 1981; Cohen and Levinthal, 1989; Malerba, 1992; Dodgson, 1993; UNCTAD, 1996; Lall, 1992). Thus, we may describe technological capabilities as the resources that are organised to generate innovations, which may be incremental or radical. With a particular focus on developing countries as importers of technologies, they described technological capability as the ability to adapt or assimilate imported technology and to incorporate the additional and distinct resources needed to manage and productively use the newly acquired technology. However, given that developing countries do not only import technologies, Bell and Pavit (1993) and Lall *et al.*, (1993) offer a more robust description of technological capability as the resources needed to generate and manage technical change. These resources, according to them, include skills, knowledge, experience as well as particular kinds of institutional configurations such as structure and linkages necessary to produce inputs for technical change. Thus, we observe that technological capability is needed by developing countries to adapt and use imported technologies and to fast track absorptive capacity. This brings into lime light the issue of technological learning. Jin and Stough (1998) define the learning capability of an agent as its capacity to create, acquire, and transform knowledge and thereby upgrade its skills, expertise and competencies. According to Biggs *et al* (1995) and Wangwe (1995), technological learning is facilitated by firms' involvement in an information-rich environment created by a dense network of relations with other firms engaged in similar activities with training opportunities and information sources that address specific business problems and with an available network of specialised consultants. Technological learning and the strategy for approaching it therefore becomes crucial for firms that have to operate imported technology. Since industrial dynamism and competitiveness depend largely on the accumulation of technological capabilities, Bell and Pavit (1993) refers to any process that strengthens those capabilities as technological learning. We however note that a firm may not be able to compete even in the local market with cheaper imports unless it has developed a solid base of local skills and its own technological efforts. This is particularly relevant to this study in that the technologies used in the oil and gas servicing firms are imported. However, we seek to investigate how learning has transpired in the sub-sector through deliberate in-house efforts and how much of these have precipitated into innovation and value addition for the nation.

Methodology

In this study, technological capability is viewed in terms of trainings and technological learning acquired to generate technological and organisational innovations. This is because the authors are interested in determining the extent to which these factors have helped the indigenous firms gain mastery of knowledge sufficiently to implement the LC policy. To this end, structured questionnaire was used to elicit information on innovation and technological efforts of the firms, their sources of information for innovation, trainings, technological learning, human resource and expenditure on R&D. This was supplemented with shop floor interview, observation and secondary data. The population of the indigenous oilfield services firms in Nigeria at the time of the study was 120 out of which 60 were purposively sampled. Descriptive statistics was used to analyse the data obtained.

Results and Discussion

The survey sampled 60 firms with 67% response rate. The main sources of technology capability evaluated in this study are the background of the head(s) of technical departments in the firm, organisational learning and the internal technological efforts of the firm (staff training and innovation expenditure).

Background of the head(s) of technical department(s)

The study noted that only 11 out of 40 have separate production and engineering departments while the remaining 29 have the production and engineering department as one single department

Production department

The result of this study showed that 52.5 % of the heads of production department in the firms surveyed have Higher National Diploma, while 20% have Bachelor Degrees, 22.5% have Masters Degree and 5% have Doctorate Degree. Also, 80% of the heads of production department have degrees in Science or Engineering field while 20% have degrees in Management or Finance-related field. Furthermore, 7.5% of the heads of technical department went for training in other African countries, 20% in Europe, 7.5% in South America, 15% in Asia and 5% in Australia at some point in time. As to where their degrees were obtained, 2.5% of the head of the production department obtained a degree in other African countries, 15% obtained degree in Europe, and 2.5% obtained degree in United States, Canada or Mexico.

Engineering department

Information gathered from this study showed that 42.5% of the heads of engineering department have Higher National Diploma, while 30% have Bachelor Degrees, 20% have Masters Degree and 7.5% have Doctorate Degree. Those who obtained degrees in Finance-related field were 77.5%. Also, 15% of the heads of engineering department went for training in other African Countries, 12.5% in Europe, 15% in United States, Canada or Mexico, 5% in South America, 12.5% in Asia and 2.5% in Australia at some point in time. While 10% of the heads of the engineering department obtained a degree in Europe, 2.5% in United States, Canada or Mexico while 2.5% of the heads of the engineering department had previously worked in other African Countries.

Types of Technological Innovations

The table below shows the types of technological innovations that had taken place in the indigenous oilfield services firms in Nigeria between 2007 and 2010.

The prevalence of organisational innovations was observed to be higher than that of all other innovation types (Table one). It was the only type of innovation that ranked high. This primarily suggests that organisational changes are at the heart of the innovation processes in the indigenous oilfield servicing sub-sector. These changes, like OECD (2005) argued, are typically expressed in business practices and workplace organisation that are new to the firm and occur as a result of strategic management decisions. The intensive prevalence of organisational innovation, alongside process innovation, within our developing country context is not surprising because organisational changes, very much like process innovations, are less risky and consume much less resources compared to other types of innovations. Concerning process innovation, Egbetokun *et al.* (2009) noted that changes in processes are less rigid, more responsive to 'shop-floor' serendipitous discoveries and may not generally require financial investments as much as product innovations.

Table one: Types of technological innovations in the indigenous oilfield services firms

	Types of Technological Innovation	Completed (%)	Started but later abandoned (%)	Never initiated (%)
Product Innovation	Introduced new product	12.5	2.5	85
	Developed new product	2.6	5.1	92.3
	Improved existing product	5.1	0	94.9
Process Innovation	Introduced new process	12.8	5.1	82.1
	Developed new process	2.6	10.3	87.2
	Improved existing process	23.1	5.1	71.8
Organisational Innovation	Introduced quality Control	42.5	7.5	50
	Introduced maintenance routine	55	10	35
	Introduced waste management procedure	37.5	15	47.5
	Reverse engineered any product/process	10.3	28.2	61.5

Source: field survey, 2011

Diffusion-Based Innovation

The study showed that 41% (16) of the firms developed/applied some new or modified versions of either product or process technology within the period 2007 and 2010. Of these 16 firms, 31.2% (5) firms developed the new or modified versions of the product or process technology with a license on their own while 62.5% (10) was through partnership with the licensor. The 41% incidence of diffusion-based innovation recorded in this study actually arose from product and process licences. This somewhat low figure is a true representation of the situation within the sub-sector. The firms in the industry are all SMEs that are mostly confronted by several resource constraints. It is therefore difficult for them to procure licences. Low levels of absorptive capacities may also explain this situation (Audretsch *et al.*, 2005; Rosa and Mohnen, 2008). The firms that have been able to do this are those having affiliation with foreign-based corporation.

Trainings and technological learning

The fact that firms require an adequate stock of skilled manpower and the role played by firm-level investments in training to enhance this pool has been established in the innovation literature (Romijn and Albaladejo, 2002; Amara *et al.*, 2008). More recent research has indeed proven that firms that continually invest in staff training tend to be more capable to innovate.

Table two: Nature of training embarked upon by the firms within the period 2007 to 2010

	2007	2008	2009	2010
Use of Information & Communication Technology	3 (7.5%)	4 (10%)	7 (17.5%)	7 (17.5%)
Repairs and Maintenance	1 (2.5%)	5 (12.5%)	12 (30%)	10 (25%)
Project Management	1 (2.5%)	2 (5%)	12 (30%)	14 (35%)
Technical Report Writing	0	1 (2.5%)	4 (10%)	2 (5%)
Industrial Safety	2 (5%)	4 (10%)	8 (210%)	8 (20%)

Source: field survey, 2011

The results in Table two showed that that the indigenous oilfield servicing firms in Nigeria were marginally active in this regard as all of the firms reported having implemented one or more staff training programmes within the period covered in this study.

Training and Innovation Expenditure

The training and innovation expenditure of the firms is given in table three below

Table Three: Training and innovation expenditure of the Firms

Expenditure (Million Naira)	2007 (%)	2008 (%)	2009 (%)	2010 (%)
<i>Training</i>				
Less than 1	10	12.5	17.5	17.5
Between 1 and 5	5	12.2	32.5	35
Between 5 and 10	Nil	Nil	Nil	5
<i>Innovation</i>				
Less than 1	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5
Between 1 and 5	5	12.5	12.5	15
Between 5 and 10	Nil	Nil	Nil	2.5

Source: field survey, 2011

Majority of the firms that engaged in staff training spent below a million naira per year but the trend became reversed as the years progressed (table three above). Like the training expenditure, the innovation expenditure increased as the years progressed.

Conclusion

The results showed that the firms demonstrated some level of technological capabilities and innovation, albeit in an uneven manner. Although some product, process and diffusion-based innovation were found, organisational innovations were at the heart of the innovation activities of the firms. It is to be concluded from these that firms operating within such contexts are not necessarily innovation-inactive.

Specifically, diffusion-based innovation was very low. The few firms that succeeded in doing this were those that on their own had significant external resource endowments by virtue of belonging to a global group or creating international ties. Most of the firms were largely unable to muster enough resources on their own to engage in activities that would give rise to that kind of innovation.

Implication of the study

For the firms, the following specific suggestions are useful for the build-up of innovation capability:

- i. On firm-level leadership, our findings imply that the possession of a university degree and previous work experience in an SME by the heads of department is very useful.
- ii. On individual level, firms are required to improve their absorptive capacities by creating regular programmes for staff development, and making the necessary investments.

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